

AWARD
Scaling autonomous logistics

D9.1
Project website and social
network account

—
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List of acronyms

C&D	Communication and Dissemination
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
H2020	Horizon 2020
KPI	Key performance Indicator
M	Month
PC	Personal Computer
R&D	Research and Development
SEO	Search Engine Optimisation
T	Task
WP	Work Package

1. Executive Summary

Within WP9 “Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation”, this deliverable D9.1 “Project website and social network account” reports on the first activities performed under T9.1 “Dissemination and communication activities”. More specifically, this deliverable presents the AWARD website and social media profiles on different platforms.

Both AWARD website and social media will:

- Promote the project’s brand identity to the relevant stakeholders;
- Make the project ambitions and results widely known;
- Serve as a news service regarding the latest project activities;
- Establish links with similar R&D initiatives and projects.

Additionally, the website will serve as an online repository of public deliverables, presentations, newsletters, and scientific publications as soon as they are produced by AWARD partners. The AWARD website, LinkedIn, Twitter and YouTube accounts have already been activated and shared with the AWARD partners during the kick-off meeting in M1 (January 2021):

- <https://award-h2020.eu/>
- <https://www.linkedin.com/company/award-h2020/>
- https://twitter.com/award_h2020
- <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCOUPgUdn7JlbUYu7MexdzfQ> .

The AWARD online presence will grow (cf. KPIs in D9.2¹) as the project activities are implemented and yield results. Therefore, the content of the project website and social media will be constantly updated and curated by the WP9 leader. However, all partners will be actively involved in communication activities to emphasize the importance of the work, and to facilitate effective communication to all the stakeholders involved in the autonomous transport system.

The project online channels serve as a means to reach the communication and dissemination strategy outlined in D9.2 “Plan for the dissemination of the results”², which also lists the key performance indicators (KPIs) related to the website and social media. Finally, D9.5 “Final dissemination plan” will update the achievement of these KPIs in M36.

¹ AWARD (2021), D9.2 “Plan for the dissemination of the results”. Available online at: <https://award-h2020.eu/index.php/public-deliverables/>

² AWARD (2021), D9.2 “Plan for the dissemination of the results”. Available online at: <https://award-h2020.eu/index.php/public-deliverables/>

2. Introduction

2.1. Framework of D9.1

Similarly to D9.2 “Plan for dissemination of the results”, this deliverable D9.1 “Project website and social network account” is the first measurable result of WP9 “Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation”. This work package acts as the main interface between the project and the outside world. The main objective is to match the project results with exploitation opportunities. Towards this goal, WP9 aims at making the project’s results widely known, establishing links with related on-going research initiatives, explore and assess emerging application areas, and set the foundations for further potential commercial exploitation and opportunities with the identified stakeholders.

D9.1 is part of T9.1 “Dissemination and communication activities”, that will develop and implement an appropriate dissemination and networking strategy and materials. More specifically, it deals with the creation and promotion of the project digital presence (project website and social networks).

2.2. Dissemination level of D9.1

D9.1 is a public deliverable presenting the AWARD website and social media profiles on different platforms to serve the dissemination plan outlined in D9.2³. The website and the social profiles will be publicly accessible by all online users and followers, who will also be able to download public deliverables, presentations, newsletters, and scientific publications for free. As all public deliverables, D9.1 will be uploaded on the dedicate webpage for free download (<https://award-h2020.eu/index.php/public-deliverables/>).

2.3. Structure of D9.1

After an executive summary in Section 1, Section 2 places D9.1 in the framework of the DoA⁴ (WP9 and T9.1). Consequently, Section 3 delves into the website design, structure and performance analysis, whereas Section 4 provides information about the project social media (LinkedIn, Twitter and YouTube). Finally, Section 5 concludes the deliverable and sheds some lights into the future of C&D activities in AWARD.

³ AWARD (2021), D9.2 “Plan for the dissemination of the results”. Available online at: <https://award-h2020.eu/index.php/public-deliverables/>

⁴ AWARD (2021), Grant Agreement.

3. AWARD Website

The project website (<https://award-h2020.eu/>) was created as the main reference point for both the AWARD partners and the external stakeholders interested in the project activities. The website will be constantly curated by the WP9 leader in cooperation with all partners engaging in C&D activities (presentations, publications, demonstrations of use cases, etc.). The AWARD website will be maintained three years after the project conclusion in order to provide all interested stakeholders with access to AWARD results and materials.

3.1. Website design

The website was built using WordPress (version 5.6.2). WordPress is a free and open-source software that allows an easy and intuitive creation and maintenance of websites. Additionally, WordPress offers free access to a wide library of plug-ins for different purposes, including SEO improvement and mailing lists management, in the case of AWARD website. The WordPress version and the installed plug-ins will be updated as soon as their new version is released.

The AWARD website is supported by Elementor, a web design plug-in characterized by highly customizable page building options. Elementor allows for the creation of user-friendly and responsive web content, that is easily accessible and comprehensible from all kinds of devices (PCs, laptops, tablets, smartphones, etc.).

The website interface addresses the fundamental needs of pleasing appearance, conceptual clarity, user-friendliness and simplicity. Furthermore, the website content is consistent with the project ambitions and results, as well as coherent with other C&D channels (e.g. social media).

3.2. Website structure

Figure 1 below shows the initial structure of the AWARD website. As the AWARD partners implement the project activities and achieve results, the website will grow and change accordingly to include the latest developments. For example, the dedicated pages on newsletters, presentations and publications will be published as soon as their content is available.

Figure 1: AWARD website structure

The website structure shown in Figure 1 is contained in the header, as well as the AWARD logo, which redirects to the homepage.

The homepage (<https://award-h2020.eu/>) presents the project acronym, full name, mission, use cases, key numbers and partners. Additionally, the homepage automatically displays the project news as soon as they are published in the dedicated webpage (<https://award-h2020.eu/index.php/category/news/>). Finally, the homepage calls the website visitor to several actions, such as further navigating through the website, subscribing to the project newsletter, following AWARD on social media and sending an email.

AWARD is thoroughly described under the menu tab “Excellence” (<https://award-h2020.eu/index.php/excellence/>) that tells more about the project vision, ambitions, objectives, results and methodology, whereas dedicated webpages have been created to list the project partners and their respective roles (<https://award-h2020.eu/index.php/partners/>), as well as the external collaborations (<https://award-h2020.eu/index.php/collaborations/>) that the project is establishing with other similar R&D projects. During the lifecycle of the project, in fact, AWARD will join forces with several similar initiatives in the field of autonomous transport system.

Finally, all pages end with a footer including the acknowledgment of the EU funding, the disclaimer, the link to the EC factsheet (<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101006817>), and to the website Privacy policy (<https://award-h2020.eu/index.php/privacy-policy/>).

Screenshots of all AWARD webpages are available in Annex 1.

3.3. Monitoring and reporting

The AWARD website will increase the general public awareness about the project activities. Therefore, the main KPI associated with the website is 3000 single visits by the end of the project (extended KPIs are available in D9.2 “Plan for the dissemination of the results”). In order to monitor the performance towards this end, the AWARD website was registered in Google Analytics, a free web analytics services enabling detailed and intuitive reports based on continuously updated statistics.

Thanks to Google Analytics, other meaningful statistics will be also available, such as:

- Users by time of day
- Session by country
- Average session duration
- Bounce rate
- Etc.

Updated reporting on the AWARD website will be provided in D9.5 “Final dissemination plan” (M36), as well as during the relevant project meetings described in D10.6 “Project management plan”⁵.

⁵ AWARD (2021), D10.6 “Project Management plan”.

4. AWARD Social media accounts

The AWARD social media profiles on LinkedIn, Twitter and YouTube will maximize the visibility of the project results and of the partners behind their achievement. Social networks will also allow followers to interact with AWARD through comments and reshare of the project posts, thus enabling a close monitoring of the feedback received, (e.g., the number and type of followers, the kind of comments and share, etc.). Similarly to the website, the project profiles on social media will be maintained after the project conclusion to allow the project's followers to access deliverables, presentations and publications.

4.1. LinkedIn

The AWARD LinkedIn profile (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/award-h2020/>) was activated in M1 (January 2021) and shared with all partners during the Kick-off meeting. AWARD will leverage the personal and group connections among users of this social media to exchange updates about the project meetings, events and results and to attract interested stakeholders in the field of autonomous transport system.

An overview of AWARD profile on LinkedIn is available in Figure 2 below:

Figure 2: AWARD LinkedIn

4.2. Twitter

The AWARD Twitter account (https://twitter.com/award_h2020) was activated in M1 (January 2021) and shared with all partners during the Kick-off meeting. This social network will serve as the main AWARD news service, posting at least weekly tweets about the project developments, the partners' activities, European initiatives, etc.

The AWARD updates will be included in the wider conversation about the project-related topics through a selection of specific hashtags, such as #IntelligentTransportSystem, #ITC, #SustainableLogistics, #SupplyChainManagement, #OperationalResearch, #Truck, #Automation, #CAV, #LogisticsOperations, #AutonomousTransportSystem, #ATS, #FleetmanagementSystem, #Demonstration, #PilotProject, #AutonomousDrivingSystem, #ADS.

An overview of AWARD account on Twitter is available in Figure 3 below:

Figure 3: AWARD Twitter

4.3. YouTube

The AWARD channel on YouTube (<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCOUPqUdn7JlbUYu7MexdzfQ>) was activated and will be populated with video contents about the project demonstrations and results as soon as they are available. In the meantime, interested users of this social media can subscribe to the

channel. Therefore, the YouTube channel will serve as a repository of promotional videos as well as a tool to attract followers.

An overview of AWARD channel on YouTube is available in Figure 4 below:

Figure 4: AWARD YouTube channel

4.4. Monitoring and reporting

The AWARD social networks will increase the visibility of the project. Therefore, the main KPIs measuring their performance are associated with the number of publications and the number of followers. More specifically:

- 1000 new followers per year in social networks;
- > 2000 tweets by M36 (December 2023)
- > 300 posts on LinkedIn
- 24h response time on social media

Extended KPIs are available in D9.2 “Plan for the dissemination of the results”⁶. All these social media provide free analytics dashboards, which will be the main source to update the project KPIs. Updated reporting on the AWARD website will be provided in D9.5 “Final dissemination plan” (M36, December 2023), as well as during the relevant project meetings as described in D10.6 “Project management plan”⁷.

⁶ AWARD (2021), D9.2 “Plan for the dissemination of the results”. Available online at: <https://award-h2020.eu/index.php/public-deliverables/>

⁷ AWARD (2021), D10.6 “Project Management plan”.

5. Conclusion

AWARD envisioned WP9 “Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation” to make the project visible and widely known and to establish links with relevant stakeholders. This deliverable D9.1 “Project website and social network account” focuses on the project online presence through the creation of a project website and three social media accounts.

This document outlined the design, structure and management of both the AWARD website and social media profile, while providing links to access them. The online presence will promote the project among relevant stakeholders, keep the followers and visitors up to date with the project activities and results and establish links with similar projects and platforms.

As the AWARD activities are implemented and results achieved, the website and social networks will be updated accordingly by the WP9 leader. However, all partners will be actively involved in seeking and engaging in C&D activities to reach the ambitious goals set by the KPIs.

The project online C&D channels are part of the communication and dissemination strategy outlined in D9.2 “Plan for the dissemination of the results”⁸, which also lists the KPIs whose achievement will be reported in D9.5 “Final dissemination plan” (M36, December 2023).

⁸ AWARD (2021), D9.2 “Plan for the dissemination of the results”. Available online at: <https://award-h2020.eu/index.php/public-deliverables/>

Annex 1: Website screenshots

Figure 5: AWARD website screenshots – homepage

Figure 6: AWARD website screenshots – excellence

Figure 7: AWARD website screenshots – partners

Figure 8: AWARD website screenshots – collaborations

Figure 9: AWARD website screenshots – deliverables

Figure 10: AWARD website screenshots – news

Figure 11: AWARD website screenshots – contacts

Privacy policy

Our commitment

We are committed to ensuring the protection of your Personal Data and your Privacy. To better protect your Privacy, we provide this page explaining our online information practices. By using our websites and/or our online pages available on platforms and social networks, you agree to the conditions of this Privacy Policy. If we change our Privacy Policy, we will post the changes on this page to keep you informed of the information we collect, how we use this information, and whether the information is shared with other parties.

What terms we use in this Privacy Policy

AWARD has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101006917. It was launched in January 2021 and is planned to run for 36 months. Its consortium comprises the following partners:

- EASYMILE
- CONTINENTAL Tires AG & CO. OHG
- KAMAG TRANSPORTTECHNIK GMBH & CO. KG
- TERBERG BENCHOP BV
- SMART AIRPORT SYSTEMS
- DEMATIC
- DROS AS
- CENTRE D'ETUDES ET D'EXPERTISE SUR LES RISQUES L'ENVIRONNEMENT LA MOBILITE ET L'AMENAGEMENT
- TEKNOLOGIAN TUTKIMUSKESKUS VTT OY
- AIT AUSTRIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY GMBH
- APPLIED AUTONOMY AS
- DIGITRANS GMBH
- ENDE SOLUTIONS .S.L
- IRU PROJECTS ASBL

Figure 12: AWARD website screenshots – privacy policy

References

- [1] AWARD (2021), D9.2 “Plan for the dissemination of the results”. Available online at: <https://award-h2020.eu/index.php/public-deliverables/>
- [2] AWARD (2021), D9.2 “Plan for the dissemination of the results”. Available online at: <https://award-h2020.eu/index.php/public-deliverables/>
- [3] AWARD (2021), D9.2 “Plan for the dissemination of the results”. Available online at: <https://award-h2020.eu/index.php/public-deliverables/>
- [4] AWARD (2021), Grant Agreement.
- [5] AWARD (2021), D10.6 “Project Management plan”.
- [6] AWARD (2021), D9.2 “Plan for the dissemination of the results”. Available online at: <https://award-h2020.eu/index.php/public-deliverables/>
- [7] AWARD (2021), D10.6 “Project Management plan”.
- [8] AWARD (2021), D9.2 “Plan for the dissemination of the results”. Available online at: <https://award-h2020.eu/index.php/public-deliverables/>